

MORPHOLOGY OF THE HEART IN DIFFERENT FORMS OF TUBERCULOSIS.

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Relevance of the topic: Tuberculosis is an airborne infection that most often affects the lungs, but can also "attack" other organs: bones, skin, intestines, and the heart. The cause of the disease is Mycobacterium tuberculosis bacteria. They cause inflammation in certain areas, resulting in the formation of nodules and foci of necrosis (ie, dead tissue) in the tissues. Because of them, the organs cannot work normally, and the body reacts with general intoxication.

If immunity or drugs do not stop the disease in time, the person may die. According to the World Health Organization, tuberculosis is one of the ten leading causes of death worldwide. The main source of infection is sick people. However, there is also a possibility of the disease being transmitted from animals.

The more sick people around, the higher the risk of infection. It is not out of the question to encounter such patients in public places in big cities. The majority of patients have a closed form of the disease, that is, the bacteria gnaw the body, but are not released into the environment.

The open form of tuberculosis is very dangerous for others (and for the patients themselves), so it is necessary to treat it in a hospital. Prolonged contact with people suffering from the open form of tuberculosis is a big risk.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, the aim of the work was to determine the morphological changes in the heart from the internal organs of the patients who died with various forms of tuberculosis at the Khorezm Branch of the Republican Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Phthisia and Pulmonology.

The results obtained: as a result of scientific research, when the bodies of patients with various forms of tuberculosis were autopsied at the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of Khorezm Region, it was found that there were morphological changes in the heart tissue from the internal organs. As a result, it was found that the patients had acute heart failure as a complication.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that when the corpses of patients who died from various forms of tuberculosis in Khorezm region were examined by autopsy, it was found that there were morphological changes in their internal organs, that is, in the heart. As a result, it was found that most patients died as a result of acute heart failure as a complication of the disease.

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